

Liquid Crystal Inorganic Hybrid Photorefractives

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Abstract - We report on the photorefractive properties of liquid crystals sandwiched between windows of cerium doped strontium barium niobate (Ce:SBN). This adaptable design has been used to create devices using pure nematic liquid crystals, ferroelectric nanoparticle doped liquid crystals, and cholesteric liquid crystals. In all these systems, modulation of the liquid crystal molecules is driven by the surface space-charge field from the inorganic windows. Owing to the large effective trap density in the Ce:SBN, high resolution gratings with two-beam coupling gain coefficients of up to 1400 cm^{-1} have been achieved in the Bragg regime.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, spectacular photorefractive advances have been reported in liquid crystal cells. These interactions can be observed in thin layers owing to the very high refractive index modulation that can be achieved through space-charge field reorientation of the liquid crystal molecules. Of particular interest has been the emergence of undoped nematic liquid crystals reoriented by photo-generated space charges in adjacent photorefractive [1] or photoconducting layers [2,3], yielding two-beam coupling gain coefficients two orders of magnitude higher than those typically seen in solid inorganic crystals. Until recently, these advances have been restricted to operation in the Raman-Nath regime, generating multiple order diffracted beams and restricting the angle between the pump and signal beams to less than a few degrees. However, recent work has demonstrated large liquid crystal gain coefficients can be achieved in the Bragg regime when the space-charge field originates from inorganic photorefractive crystals used as windows for undoped nematic liquid crystal cells [4,5]. The origin of the large unidirectional gain in the liquid crystal layer has been demonstrated to arise from a combination of local surface induced pre-tilt of the liquid crystal molecules together with splay-induced flexopolarization of the nematic liquid crystal [5,6]. A pre-tilt of the liquid crystal molecular surface alignment is necessary to permit spatial frequency matching of the optical interference pattern and the resulting index grating, while splay induced flexopolarization permits the otherwise nematic material to become sensitive to the *sign* of the space-charge field.

In this paper we report on improvements to hybrid organic-inorganic photorefractives through the use of a nematic or cholesteric liquid crystal layers used either in their pure state

or doped with a low concentration of ferroelectric nanoparticles of barium titanate.

II. EXPERIMENT

20 mm x 20 mm x 1.3 mm uncoated inorganic crystals of strontium barium niobate doped with 0.01 weight % cerium (Ce:SBN) were used as windows for the liquid crystal cells, with the crystal c-axis parallel to one of the 20 mm long edges. Cells were fabricated using either one Ce:SBN window and one glass window, or with two Ce:SBN windows. The inside surface of each window was spin coated with a nylon multipolymer (Elvamide® 8023R, supplied by DuPont, prepared as a 0.125 weight % solution in anhydrous methanol), followed by uni-axially rubbing using a nylon roller. The cell windows were held together using simple spring clips and the cell spacing was defined by glass beads dispersed at low concentration in the liquid crystal medium.

The hybrid cell was placed at the overlap of pump and signal beams and oriented approximately normal to the bisector of the two beams with the c-axis of each window in the plane of the incident p-polarization. The pump beam power at the hybrid cell was 10 mW and the signal power was $7 \mu\text{W}$, with both spot sizes identical at $4 \text{ mm } 1/e^2$ diameter. The c-axes directions were such that the signal beam was amplified by the Ce:SBN. Prior to filling with liquid crystals, the gain of the cell filled with oil of a similar refractive index to the liquid crystals was measured as a function of grating spacing to provide reference gain characteristics of the Ce:SBN windows. After cleaning and re-coating the cell windows, the cell was filled with liquid crystals and the gain measurements repeated. For each grating spacing the gain of the liquid crystal was determined by dividing the liquid crystal filled cell gain by the oil filled cell gain. The gain coefficient, Γ , for the liquid crystal is then given by $\Gamma = \log_e(G)/d$ where G is the small signal gain and d is thickness of the liquid crystal layer. Liquid crystal solutions were prepared using either a pure nematic (TL205), pure cholesteric mixtures (either BL038 or TL205 with CB15 chiral dopant), or corresponding solutions doped with low concentrations (up to 1 weight %) of BaTiO_3 nanoparticles prepared by wet milling in a zirconia ball mill in the presence of a surfactant (oleic acid). The nanoparticle sizes were controlled by adjusting the ball milling duration, yielding average diameters from 50 nm to 9 nm.

III. NANOPARTICLE RESULTS

The optimum BaTiO₃ nanoparticle diameter was found to be approximately 11.6 nm. Figure 1 compares the optical gain characteristics of nematic hybrid cells doped with various concentrations of BaTiO₃ nanoparticles. It is clear that the added nanoparticles dramatically influenced the optical gain characteristics, increasing the magnitude of the gain and reversing the *sign* of the beam coupling. These effects became progressively more pronounced as the nanoparticle concentration is increased. The maximum gain coefficient reached 1100 cm⁻¹, an extremely large value for *Bragg matched* two-beam coupling. We did not observe any Raman-Nath diffraction during these measurements.

Figure 1 – Small signal gain coefficient vs. grating spacing for TL205/BaTiO₃ mixture concentrations

The dramatic effect of the nanoparticles is intriguing, especially the reversal of the sign of the beam coupling gain. We have eliminated contributions from screening charges and liquid crystal pre-tilt variations from being responsible for the altered gain characteristics. We propose that the most likely mechanism for the gain reversal and magnitude increase is from the ferroelectric domain structure of the BaTiO₃ nanoparticles. Since the splay-induced flexopolarization effectively polarizes the liquid crystal molecules, we can speculate that any single domain nanoparticles may align with their spontaneous polarization directions anti-parallel to the TL205 flexopolarization. The external space-charge field will try to rotate the LC molecules and the nanoparticles in *opposite* directions. Assuming strong anchoring between the liquid crystal molecules and the dispersed BaTiO₃ nanoparticles, it is plausible that the nanoparticles may drag the liquid crystal directors in the direction opposite to that which would apply for pure LC with the same flexoelectric polarization and alignment conditions, resulting in a reversal of the cell gain coefficient. From published values of the spontaneous polarization of BaTiO₃ nanoparticles [7], we estimate the product of the particle polarization and the local space-charge field to be in the range of 10⁰ to 10³ greater than the equivalent product for the flexoelectric term for pure TL205. Under these conditions, the addition of the nanoparticles should be expected to both reverse the sign of

the beam coupling and to increase the beam coupling magnitude, as we have observed.

IV. CHOLESTERIC RESULTS

Figure 2 compares the liquid crystal gain characteristics obtained by using either one or two Ce:SBN windows and a 5 μm thick cholesteric layer. For this arrangement, a mixture with the centre of the reflective notch positioned at 440 nm was used to ensure the polarization remained linear and parallel to the crystal c-axes in each Ce:SBN window. The gain characteristics for the double window cell contrast sharply with those obtained from single Ce:SBN window cells. Most surprising was the complete inversion of the gain characteristics such that the gain coefficient slope with grating spacing was positive for the dual window device and negative for the single window device. The increased gain magnitude, exceeding 1400 cm⁻¹ in the Bragg regime, from the dual window devices is easier to understand qualitatively, since there are now two windows contributing to the net space-charge field. However, the reason for the gain inversion remains unclear at this time.

Figure 2 – Small signal gain coefficient vs. grating spacing for single and dual window cholesteric mixtures of BL038 and CB15

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